

Digital India: the move towards E-Government Transformation

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Abstract

The governments around the globe are rapidly transforming to establish themselves as E-Governments. The Government of India is also moving towards E-government transformation. Digital India initiative of the government is an umbrella program which not only facilitates e-government transformation but also focuses on transforming the lives of citizens and inclusive development. Digital India is a unique idea in the sense that provides a combined vision and a comprehensive execution plan, bringing together various departments as well as existing and new programs that are monitored and influenced centrally by the government. This paper provides a comprehensive review of this flagship programme understanding the e-government transformation through this programme. This paper highlights the difference between e-government and traditional government. It also highlights the initiatives of the e-government transformation in the Digital India Programme.

Keywords: E-government; E-governance; Digital India; E-Government transformation; E-Citizen

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Full Text:

E-Government:

E-Government is the modernisation of processes and functions of the government using the tools of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) so as to transform the way it serves its constituents. In other words, it is the application of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to the process of government functionalities for *Good Governance*. It is an initiative to achieve better government through the electronic and sophisticated transformation of the traditional government operations and functions to an efficient, effective, transparent and accountable government. It is also an initiative to positively alter the relationship of the government with the public through public participation and engagement and better information and service delivery.¹

E-government consists of the digital interactions between a citizen and their government (C2G), between governments and government agencies (G2G), between government and citizens (G2C), between government and employees (G2E), and between government and businesses/Commerce (G2B). This digital interaction consists of e-citizen at all levels of government (city, state/province,

¹ Chandra, S. (2016). *E-Government in India: The need to ponder current e-government uptake*. S O C R A T E S, 4(3), 35-46. Retrieved from <http://socratesjournal.com/index.php/socrates/article/view/236>

national, and international), governance, information and communication technology (ICT), and business process reengineering (BPR).(Jeong (2007) Fundamental of Development Administration. Selangor: Scholar Press. ISBN 978-967-5-04508-0)

In simple words, E-government is a complete transformation of the process of governance and government functionalities, for efficient, effective, transparent and accountable delivery of information and services to the citizens and Business/Commerce.

E-government is different from the traditional form of Government. E-Government is a complete transformation of Governmental functionality. It is a paradigm shift, from what has been in function since last two hundred years to what is the demand of this digital era. It is not just computerization or digitalization of the government offices and record keeping practices or use of Information technology in the governmental business but, instead it is the transformation of government which redefines the role of government and its relation to the citizens. It is a reconstruction and a re-engineering of government that brings with it significant change and empowers citizens. It is an initiative to achieve better government through the electronic and sophisticated transformation of the traditional government operations and functions to an efficient, effective, transparent and accountable government. It is also an initiative to positively alter the relationship of the government with the public through public participation and engagement and better information and service.

This transformation consists of *e-citizen* at all levels of government.² An e-citizen is digitally empowered, who can usher in the era of e-government transformation and make use as well as participate in the governance process in a much better way.

² Jeong (2007) Fundamental of Development Administration. Selangor: Scholar Press. (ISBN 978-967-5-04508-0)

The current endeavour and effort of government Informatization (E-Government transformation) worldwide are focused on the following four objectives³:

1. To pursue higher effectiveness, efficiency and productivity.
2. To build up a more transparent, honest and clean government.
3. To provide better services to businesses and citizens.
4. To establish new types of partnerships with business and citizens in order to build a more democratic and people-centred society.

Table 1: Difference between E-government and traditional form of government

	E-government	Traditional form of government
Government structure and functionality; and Service delivery	Based on Info-structure: 1. e-Records 2. Authentication and Digital Signature 3. e-Payment (digital) 4. Portal – Web-based (electronic) government.	Based on classical/Weberian structure and functions: 1. Written paper-based records 2. Non E-payment 3. Office based government 4. Process and procedures.
Citizens	E-Literate and Digitally empowered (E-Citizens)	No such requirement
Economy	Digital/Electronic	Non-Digital/traditional paper currency/cheque based
Interactions between citizen and government (C2G)	Digital/Electronic	Non-Digital/traditional paper based
Interactions between governments and government agencies (G2G)	Digital/Electronic	Non-Digital/traditional paper based

³Dr. Hongren Zhou and Ms. Chen Gu. Principles of E-Government What a Government Leader Should Know - Part I. United Nations Public Administration Network Publication.

Interactions between government and citizens (G2C)	Digital/Electronic	Non-Digital/traditional paper based
Interactions between government and employees (G2E)	Digital/Electronic	Non-Digital/traditional paper based
Interactions between government and businesses/commerce (G2B)	Digital/Electronic	Non-Digital/traditional paper based
Movement of Democracy	Towards e-democracy	Stabilising Democratic values
Citizens participation in Governance	Digital/Electronic	Non-Digital/traditional
Use of ICT in Governance	Digital Government/ Based on ICT	Low
Business process reengineering (BPR)	Required at all levels of governance	Not mandatory
Focus	e-citizen-centred and e-service-oriented	citizen-centred and service-oriented government

Digital India

The Digital India programme is a flagship programme of the Government of India with a vision to *transform India* into a digitally empowered society and knowledge economy.⁴

The vision of Digital India:

The Vision of Digital India is centred on 3 Key Areas⁵

1. Digital Infrastructure as a Utility to Every Citizen.	– Move towards E-government transformation.
2. Governance & Services on Demand	– Move towards E-government transformation.

⁴ Introduction | Digital India Programme. (2017). Digitalindia.gov.in. Retrieved 13 June 2017, from <http://www.digitalindia.gov.in/content/introduction>

⁵ Vision and Vision Areas | Digital India Programme. (2017). Digitalindia.gov.in. Retrieved 15 June 2017, from <http://www.digitalindia.gov.in/content/vision-and-vision-areas>

3. Digital Empowerment of Citizens	– Move towards E-government transformation.
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Pillars of Digital India⁶:

Digital India is an umbrella programme that covers multiple Government Ministries and Departments. It weaves together a large number of ideas and thoughts into a single, comprehensive vision so that each of them can be implemented as part of a larger goal. Each individual element stands on its own but is also part of the larger picture. Digital India aims to provide the much-needed thrust to the nine pillars of growth areas, namely:

1. Broadband Highways
2. Universal Access to Mobile Connectivity
3. Public Internet Access Programme
4. *E-Governance: Reforming Government through Technology*
5. *E-Kranti - Electronic Delivery of Services*
6. Information for All
7. Electronics Manufacturing
8. IT for Jobs
9. Early Harvest Programmes.

Each of these areas is a complex programme in itself and cuts across multiple Ministries and Departments.⁷ All these pillars are inter-connected in the sense that they facilitate the transformation, not only the transformation of the governmental machinery but also the lives of the citizens.

Understanding the “E-Government *Transformation*” through Digital India:

Digital India aims to facilitate *e-government transformation* and, to a large extent, a transformation by Informatization through all its pillars especially the pillar of *e-Governance: Reforming*

⁶ Programme Pillars | Digital India Programme. (2017). Digitalindia.gov.in. Retrieved 15 June 2017, from <http://digitalindia.gov.in/content/programme-pillars>

⁷ Ibid

Government through Technology and e-Kranti - Electronic Delivery of Services. The Digital India is *transformational in nature* and would ensure that Government services are available to citizens electronically. It would also bring in public accountability through mandated delivery of government's services electronically; a Unique ID and e-Pramaan based on authentic and standard based interoperable and integrated government applications and data basis.⁸

Digital India aims to provide Governance & Services on Demand:

- Seamlessly integrated services across departments or jurisdictions
- Availability of services in real time from online & mobile platforms
- All citizen entitlements to be portable and available on the cloud
- Digitally transformed services for improving ease of doing business
- Making financial transactions electronic & cashless
- Leveraging Geospatial Information Systems (GIS) for decision support systems & development.

Digital India aims Digital Empowerment of Citizens as e-Government transformation consists of *e-citizen* at all levels of government. The Digital India program will empower the citizens:

- Through Universal digital literacy
- Through facilitating universally accessible digital resources
- Through availability of digital resources/services in Indian languages
- Through Collaborative digital platforms for participative governance
- Through an electronic mechanism in which Citizens are not required to physically submit Govt. documents/certificates.

It aims to provide Digital Infrastructure as a *Utility* to Every Citizen

- Availability of high-speed internet as a core utility for delivery of services to citizens
- Cradle to grave digital identity that is unique, lifelong, online and authenticable to every citizen

⁸ Digital India – A programme to transform India into digital empowered society and knowledge economy. (2017). Pib.nic.in. Retrieved 13 June 2017, from <http://pib.nic.in/newsite/PrintRelease.aspx?relid=108926>

- Mobile phone & bank account enabling citizen participation in digital & financial space
- Easy access to a Common Service Centre
- Shareable private space on a public cloud
- Safe and secure cyberspace.

E-Governance – Reforming Government through Technology:

The E-Government structure and functionality; and Service delivery is entirely based upon following info-structures:

1. e-Records
2. Authentication and Digital Signature
3. e-Payment (digital Payment)
4. Portal – Web-based (electronic) government.

The Digital India programme focuses on establishment and strengthening of these info-structures. It also focuses on the Government Process Re-engineering by using Information Technology to simplify and make the government processes more efficient is critical for transformation to make the delivery of government services more effective across various government domains and therefore needs to be implemented by all Ministries/ Departments.

The guiding principles for reforming Government through technology are⁹:

- Form simplification and field reduction – Forms should be made simple and user-friendly and only minimum and necessary information should be collected.
- Online applications and tracking - Online applications and tracking of their status should be provided.

⁹ e-Governance – Reforming Government through Technology | Digital India Programme. (2017). Digitalindia.gov.in. Retrieved 14 June 2017, from <http://digitalindia.gov.in/content/e-governance-%E2%80%93-reforming-government-through-technology>

- Online repositories - Use of online repositories e.g. for certificates, educational degrees, identity documents, etc. should be mandated so that citizens are not required to submit these documents in physical form.
- Integration of services and platforms – Integration of services and platforms e.g. Aadhaar platform of Unique Identity Authority of India (UIDAI), payment gateway, Mobile Seva platform, sharing of data through open Application Programming Interfaces (API) and middleware such as National and State Service Delivery Gateways (NSDG/SSDG) should be mandated to facilitate integrated and interoperable service delivery to citizens and businesses.
- All databases and information should be in electronic form and not manual. The workflow inside government departments and agencies should be automated to enable efficient government processes and also to allow visibility of these processes to citizens. IT should be used to automate, respond and analyse data to identify and resolve persistent problems. These would be largely processed improvements.

All these guiding principles lead towards establishment and strengthening of the info-structures to ensure efficient, effective, transparent and accountable electronic delivery of information and services to the citizens.

e-Kranti (Transforming e-Governance for Transforming Governance)

To meet the need for transforming e-Governance and to promote mobile Governance and Good Governance in the country, the approach and key components of e-Kranti were approved by the Union Cabinet on 25.03.2015 with the vision of “*Transforming e-Governance for Transforming Governance*”.

The key principles of e-Kranti are as follows¹⁰:

¹⁰ eKranti | Digital India Programme. (2017). Digitalindia.gov.in. Retrieved 14 June 2017, from <http://digitalindia.gov.in/content/ekranti>

1. **Transformation and not Translation** - All project proposals in e-Kranti must involve substantial transformation in the quality, quantity and manner of delivery of services and significant enhancement in productivity and competitiveness.
2. **Integrated Services and not Individual Services** - A common middleware and integration of the back end processes and processing systems is required to facilitate integrated service delivery to citizens.
3. **Government Process Reengineering (GPR) to be mandatory in every MMP** - To mandate GPR as the essential first step in all new MMPs without which a project may not be sanctioned. The degree of GPR should be assessed and enhanced for the existing MMPs.
4. **ICT Infrastructure on Demand** – Government departments should be provided with ICT infrastructures, such as connectivity, cloud and mobile platform on demand. In this regard, National Information Infrastructure (NII), which is at an advanced stage of project formulation, would be fast-tracked by DeitY.
5. **Cloud by Default** – The flexibility, agility and cost effectiveness offered by cloud technologies would be fully leveraged while designing and hosting applications. Government Cloud shall be the default cloud for Government Departments. All sensitive information of Government Departments shall be stored in a Government Cloud only. Any Government Department may use a private cloud only after obtaining permission from Department of Electronics and Information Technology which shall do so after assessing the security and privacy aspects of the proposed cloud.
6. **Mobile First** - All applications are designed/ redesigned to enable delivery of services through mobile.
7. **Fast Tracking Approvals** – To establish a fast-track approval mechanism for MMPs, once the Detailed Project Report (DPR) of a project is approved by the Competent Authority, Empowered Committees may be constituted with delegated powers to take all subsequent decisions.
8. **Mandating Standards and Protocols** – Use of e-Governance standards and protocols as notified by DeitY be mandated in all e-governance projects.

9. **Language Localisation** - It is imperative that all information and services in e-Governance projects are available in Indian languages as well.
10. **National GIS (Geo-Spatial Information System)** - NGIS to be leveraged as a platform and as a service in e-Governance projects.
11. **Security and Electronic Data Preservation** - All online applications and e-services to adhere to prescribed security measures including cyber security. The National Cyber Security Policy 2013 notified by DeitY must be followed.

All newly approved as well as on-going e-Governance projects will now have to follow the key principles of e-Kranti, for better delivery of Services *electronically*. There are around 44 Mission Mode Projects under e-Kranti programme. These mission mode projects (MMP's) are grouped into Central, State and Integrated projects.

Table 2: Central Mission Mode Projects (# New MMP)		
Sl. No.	Project	Line Ministry/ Department Responsible
01	Income Tax	M/o Finance/Central Board of Direct Tax
02	Passport	M/o External Affairs
03	MCA21	M/o Company Affairs
04	Insurance	D/o Financial Services
05	National Citizen Database	M/o Home Affairs/Registrar General of India (RGI)
06	Central Excise	D/o Revenue/Central Board of Excise & Custom
07	Pensions	D/o Pensions & Pensioners welfare & Dept. of Expenditure
08	Banking	D/o Financial Services

Table 2: Central Mission Mode Projects (# New MMP)		
Sl. No.	Project	Line Ministry/ Department Responsible
09	e-Office	D/o Administrative Reforms & Public Grievances
10	Posts	D/o Posts
11	Visa & Immigration	M/o Home Affairs
12	e-Sansad#	Ministry of Parliamentary Affairs
13	Common IT Roadmap for Para Military Forces#	M/o Home affairs

Source: eKranti | Digital India Programme. (2017). Digitalindia.gov.in

Table 3: State Mission Mode Projects(# New MMP)		
01	Land Records	M/o Rural Development
02	Road Transport	M/o Road Transport & Highway
03	Property Registration	D/o Land Resources and D/o Electronics and Information Technology
04	Agriculture	D/o Agriculture & Cooperation
05	Treasuries	M/o Finance
06	Municipalities	M/o Urban Development and Poverty Alleviation
07	Gram Panchayats	M/o Panchayati Raj
08	Commercial Taxes	M/o Finance

09	Police (UTs initially)	M/o Home affairs
10	Employment Exchanges	M/o Labour & Employment
11	School Education	D/o School Education and Literacy
12	Health	D/o Health and Family Welfare
13	PDS	D/o Food and Public Distribution
14	e-Vidhaan#	Ministry of Parliamentary Affairs
15	Agriculture 2.0#	D/o Agriculture
16	Rural Development#	D/o Rural Development
17	Women and Child Development#	M/o Women and Child Development

Source: eKranti | Digital India Programme. (2017). Digitalindia.gov.in

Table 4: Integrated Mission Mode Projects(# New MMP)		
01	EDI (E-Commerce)	M/o Commerce & Industry
02	E-Biz	D/o Industrial Policy & Promotion
03	Common Services Centres	D/o Electronics and Information Technology
04	India Portal	D/o Electronics and Information Technology and D/o Administrative Reforms & Public Grievances
05	E-Courts	D/o Justice
06	E-Procurement	M/o Commerce & Industry/ DGS&D
07	National Service Delivery Gateway	D/o Electronics and Information Technology

08	Financial Inclusion#	D/o Financial Services
09	National Geographical Information System#	D/o Science & Technology
10	Social Benefits#	M/o Social Justice and Empowerment as the leader and other welfare departments as co-owners
11	Roads and Highways Information System (RAHI) #	M/o Road Transport & Highways
12	e-Bhasha #	D/o Electronics and Information Technology
13	National Mission on Education Through ICT (NMEICT) #	D/o Higher Education
14	Urban Governance #	Ministry of Urban Development

Source: e-Kranti | Digital India Programme. (2017). Digitalindia.gov.in

Other than the above mentioned MMP's Digital India's E-Kranti programme has provisions for e-Education, e-Healthcare, Technology for Farmers, Technology for Security, Technology for Justice, Technology for Financial Inclusion and Technology for Cyber Security.

Conclusion:

Digital India initiatives for *e-government transformation* are almost huge and revolutionary. These initiatives not only focus on the e-government transformation by establishing info-structures, for electronic delivery of information and services but also focus on empowering the citizens. So far most of the initiatives have met with success¹¹, at least in the initial phase. Their success in the future will depend on how the policymakers, the executive and the citizens, alike, cope with the

¹¹ Status of MMPs | Digital India Programme. (2017). Digitalindia.gov.in. Retrieved 14 June 2017, from <http://digitalindia.gov.in/content/status-mmps>

numerous challenges that present themselves at various stages. If implemented properly it will transform the Government and the way in which citizens connect with the government. E-government transformation and digital empowerment of citizens will ensure clean and flawless governance and boost public participation in governance.

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